

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1*

Compd. no.	R	R'	Yield %	M p. °C	Mol. formula
1a	C ₆ H ₅ OCH ₃	2,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃	78	125	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S
1b	C ₆ H ₅ OCH ₃	2-C ₆ H ₄ N	64	65	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S
1c	C ₆ H ₅ OCH ₃	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	88	140	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S
1d	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	2,4-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	61	110	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S
1e	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	70	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ ClN ₂ O ₂ S
1f	3-CH ₃ -4-Cl.C ₆ H ₃ OCH ₃	2,4-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	65	120	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S
1g	3-CH ₃ -4-Cl.C ₆ H ₃ OCH ₃	2-C ₆ H ₄ N	83	178	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂ S
1h	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ OCH ₃	2,4-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	58	85	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S
1i	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ OCH ₃	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	76	110	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₂ S
1j	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	2,4-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	68	148	C ₆ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ N ₂ OS
1k	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	2-C ₆ H ₄ N	94	194	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS
1l	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	92	121	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₂ OS
1m	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	2-C ₁₀ H ₇	86	112	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ OS

*All compounds showed satisfactory elemental analyses for N and S.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2 AND 3*

Compd. no	R	Yield %	M p. °C	Mol. formula
2a	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	91	180	C ₄₄ H ₃₄ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₆ S ₂
2b	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	72	215	C ₄₆ H ₄₀ N ₆ O ₆ S ₂
2c	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	82	190	C ₄₄ H ₃₈ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
3a	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	78	140	C ₂₄ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
3b	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	65	102	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
3c	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	81	186	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂

*All compounds showed satisfactory elemental analyses for N and S.

Fungicidal screening: All compounds were screened for their fungicidal activity by agar-growth technique⁵ against *A. flavus*, *C. sacchari* and *H. oryzae* at three different concentrations, viz. 1000, 100 and 10 ppm.

The results obtained at concentration of 10 ppm after 96 h showed that all the compounds display fairly good level of fungicidal activity against all three fungi but are slightly less active against *C. sacchari* than against *A. flavus* and *H. oryzae*. The piperazines/benzidines are less fungicidal than the corresponding mono-Mannich bases. The introduction of a benzidine moiety in place of a piperazine and a *p*-hydroxybenzylidene group in a place of methyleno group does not show any marked effect on the fungicidal activity. In general, the compounds having chlorophenoxy or *p*-chloro-*m*-methyl phenoxy moiety at position-5 are more fungicidal.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Head, Department of Chemistry for facilities. Two of the authors (A. S. and S. K. S.) acknowledge financial assistance from U.G.C., New Delhi.

References

1. D. J. JONES, S. SQUIRES and K. R. H. WOOLRIDGE, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1965, 8, 676; N. H. SHAH, V. M. PATAKI and M. Y. MHADELKAR *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1962, 21, 76; H. SINGH and L. D. S. YADAV, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 1143; S. P. SUMAN and S. C. BAHEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 712; T. RAMALINGAN, A. A. DESHMUKH and P. S. SATTUR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 269; B. K. PATTANAYAK, D. N. ROUT and G. N. MAHAPATRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1978, 16, 1030; A. K. SENGUPTA, M. GARG and U. CHANDRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 1230.
2. S. BAHADUR and K. K. PANDEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 1138.
3. A. E. LIPKIN, I. S. CHICHKANOVA and T. A. DEGTYAREVA, *Khim. Farm. Zh.*, 1970, 4, 18 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1971, 74, 12725).
4. R. W. YOUNG and K. H. WOOD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 400.
5. J. G. HORSFALL, *Bot. Rev.*, 1945, 5, 357.

Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of some Bis-1,3,4-oxadiazoles

M. K. JANI, B. R. SHAH, N. K. UNDAVIA
and
P. B. TRIVEDI*

University Department of Chemistry, Bhavnagar University,
Bhavnagar-364 002

Manuscript received 6 February 1990, accepted 30 March 1990

MANY 5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles possess various biological activities¹. Acid hydrazides and their condensed products are also associated with biological activities^{2, 3}. All these facts led us to undertake the synthesis and antimicrobial activities of the titled compounds.

The dihydrazide of malonic acid⁴, various substituted malonanilic acid hydrazides² and bis-(5-mercapto-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)methane⁵ (1) were

prepared by the reported methods. Compound 1 on heating with various substituted malonanilic acid hydrazides in ethanol afforded the titled compounds 2.

The constitution of compounds 1 and 2 were supported by their elemental analysis, ir and pmr spectra. The ir weak band of 1 appearing at 2570 cm^{-1} (SH) disappeared in the spectra of 2 and a new peak appeared at 3160 cm^{-1} (NH) which proved the conversion of 1 into 2. Moreover, 2 showed characteristic ir bands at 1280 (N-N=C) , $1490\text{ (conjugated cyclic system -C=N)}$, $1120\text{ (C-O-C ether linkage)}$, 1630 (-NHCO) , $1430\text{ (CH}_2\text{)}$, 1240 (N-N) , 3160 (NH) and 780 cm^{-1} (*p*-substituted-benzene). The structure was also confirmed by pmr spectra of both the compounds. The pmr spectrum gave a singlet $1\delta\ 2.9$ (s, CH_2) and 3.6 (s, SH); $2\delta\ 2.9$ (s, CH_2), $9.2-9.6$ (NH) and $7.0-7.4$ (ArH).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds was checked on tlc. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (DMSO-D_6) on a Varian EM-360L spectrometer.

Bis(5-substituted-malonanilic acid hydrazido-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)methanes (2): To bis(5-mercapto-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)methane (1; 0.01 mol) was dissolved in ethanol (99%; 30 ml) was added substituted malonanilic acid hydrazide (0.02 mol) and the mixture was refluxed for 5-6 h. The excess ethanol was distilled off and the resulting solid which separated on cooling, was recrystallised from absolute ethanol (Table 1).

Pharmacological screening: The compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* by the cup-plate method⁶. Representative compounds have been screened for antitubercular activity against the human virulent strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* ($\text{H}_3\text{7R}_v$) by the absolute concentration method⁷.

Out of 15 compounds screened, 7 compounds were found active against *S. aureus* and 6 com-

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2*

Sl. no.	R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	2- CH_3 - C_6H_4	$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_6$	194	71
2.	3- CH_3 - C_6H_4	$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_6$	223	64
3.	4- CH_3 - C_6H_4	$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_6$	229	70
4.	2- OCH_3 - C_6H_4	$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_6$	248	57
5.	3- OCH_3 - C_6H_4	$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_6$	203	65
6.	4- OCH_3 - C_6H_4	$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_6$	208	66
7.	2,4-(CH_3) ₂ - C_6H_3	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_6$	212	57
8.	3,4-(CH_3) ₂ - C_6H_3	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_6$	162	54
9.	2- OC_2H_5 - C_6H_4	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_6$	196	58
10.	4- OC_2H_5 - C_6H_4	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_6$	221	63
11.	2- Cl - C_6H_4	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{20}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_6$	238	59
12.	3- Cl - C_6H_4	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{20}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_6$	156	58
13.	4- Cl - C_6H_4	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{20}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_6$	216	64
14.	2- NO_2 - C_6H_4	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_{10}$	173	57
15.	3- NO_2 - C_6H_4	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_{10}\text{O}_{10}$	231	65

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

pounds are active against *E. coli*; and 3 compounds were found active against both the species. Compounds having 2,4-dimethylphenyl, 4-ethoxyphenyl and 3-nitrophenyl substituents were found active against both the species. The compounds showed antibacterial activity in the order substituents; dimethylphenyl > ethoxyphenyl > nitrophenyl > chlorophenyl > methylphenyl > methoxyphenyl.

Out of 6 compounds screened (sl nos. 3, 4, 8, 10, 13 and 15; Table 1), none of the compounds were found active at lower concentration ($35\ \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) and 4 compounds active at higher concentration ($100\ \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$). 4-Substituted-phenyl compounds were found more active than that of 2- and 3-substituted-phenyl at higher concentration. Compounds having dimethylphenyl substituents was also active at higher concentration.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Bhavnagar University for facilities, to the Ministry of Higher Education, Government of Gujarat, for research scholarship to one of them (M.K.J.) and to Dr. S.B. Trivedi, Ex-Director, Tuberculosis Research Centre, Amargadh, for biological screening.

References

- V. S. JOLLY and V. SINGHAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 724; J. MATIVIER and R. BOESCH, Fr. Pat. 1 337 286/1963 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1964, 60, 4157); H. SAIKACHI, Brit. Pat. 9 49 288/1964 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1964, 60, 10692); I. HIRAO, Y. KATO and T. HIROTA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1971, 44, 1923; A. P. SWAIN, US Pat. 2 883 391/1959 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1959 53, 161157).
- A. K. DHAWAN, V. HORA and I. M. HORA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 199.
- F. FUJIKAWA, K. NAKAJIMA, A. TOKUOKA, V. HITOSA, T. OMETAU, T. HATSUDE and M. FUJITAL, *J. Pharm. Soc. Jpn.*, 1954, 74, 884 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1954, 48, 12887); R. CAVIER and R. RIPS, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1965, 8, 706; T. S. GARNER, R. WEINS and LEC, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 1516; Brit. Pat. 1 085 474/1947.

4. R. J. W CREMLYN and J. L. TURNER, *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1970, 2629.
5. V K MISHRA and S. C. BAHTEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 60, 867.
6. F. KAVANAGH, "Analytical Microbiology", Academic, New York, 1963, p. 126.
7. G. CANETTI, *Bull. Wld. Health Org.*, 1963, 29, 565.

Synthesis of some Substituted-dibenzodiazepinones. A Tricyclic System

M. A. LIKHATE and P. S. FERNANDES*

Department of Chemistry, St. Xavier's College,
Bombay-400 001

Manuscript received 11 September 1989 revised 25 January 1990,
accepted 30 March 1990

THERE has been some remarkable advances made on seven-membered azepine systems like benzodiazepine¹, dibenzodiazepine² etc. as psychopharmacological agents. This led us to synthesise a few such linearly substituted diazepines.

The substituted dibenzodiazepine (3) was synthesised by reacting 3-(*o*-aminoanilino)-5,5-dimethyl-2-cyclohexen-1-one (2) (2 was obtained by condensation of *o*-phenylenediamine and dimedone) with various substituted thiazole aldehydes (1) followed by *in situ* cyclisation in presence of ethanol containing small amount of acetic acid (Scheme 1). The reactivity of 2 with the aldehyde (1) is attributed to its enaminone structure in which 2-position is reactive towards electrophilic reagents³. The structures of the compounds were confirmed by elemental and spectral data.

Scheme 1

Experimental

4-Chloromethyl-2-(*N*-acetyl-*N*-2,5-dichlorophenyl)thiazole : 2,5-Dichlorophenylthiourea (2 g, 0.009

mol) was treated with 1,3-dichloroacetone (1.2 g, 0.009 mol) in dry acetone for 24 h at room temperature with stirring. The excess acetone was distilled off under reduced pressure. The crude product was treated with acetic anhydride (2.8 g, 0.3 mol) under reflux for 1.5 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and poured into water and extracted with CHCl₃. The chloroform extract was dried (Na₂SO₄), filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure. The gummy residue was passed through silica gel (35 g) column using CHCl₃ as eluant. The resulting solid was crystallised from acetonitrile (70%), m.p. 115°.

4-Formyl-2-(*N*-acetyl-*N*-2,5-dichlorophenyl)thiazole (1) : A mixture of 1 (2 g, 0.00596 mol) and hexamethylene tetramine (2.5 g, 0.018 mol) in 50% acetic acid (15 cm³) was refluxed for 1 h at 130°–40°. The reaction mixture was cooled and neutralised with aqueous NaHCO₃ and extracted with CHCl₃. The dried CHCl₃ extract on evaporation yielded a brown oil which was purified over silica gel (30 g) column using CHCl₃ as eluant. The resulting solid was recrystallised from CHCl₃–MeOH (1 : 1), (50%), m.p. 142°; *M*⁺ 316, 318 (due to Cl atoms); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 670, 1 690 (CHO), 1 590 (N–COCH₃) and 1 480 cm⁻¹ (aromatic); δ (CDCl₃) 2.1 (3H, s, N–COCH₃), 7.4 (2H, s, assigned as 'b'), 7.8 (1H, s, assigned as 'a') and 9.7 (1H, s, CHO).

3,3-Dimethyl-2,3,4,4,5,10,11-hexahydro-11-(2-*N*-acetyl-*N*-2,5-dichlorophenylthiazolyl)-1H-dibenzo[b,e][1,4]diazepine-1-one (3; R₁=R₃=Cl, R₂=H) : To a solution of 2 (1 g, 0.0043 mol) in ethanol were added the aldehyde (1; 1.4 g, 0.00435 mol) and a drop of acetic acid. The solution was refluxed for 1 h and cooled. The resulting solid was crystallised from CHCl₃–MeOH (1 : 1), (54%), m.p. 245°; *M*⁺ 526, 28 (due to Cl atoms); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 290, 3 310 (NH), 1 690 (α,β -unsat. 6-mem. ketone), 1 580, 1 540, 1 500 cm⁻¹ (aromatic); δ (CHCl₃) 1.1 (6H, s, 2×t-CH₃), 1.9 (3H, s, N–CO–CH₃), 2.15 (2H, s, CH₂ at C₄), 2.35 (2H, s, CH₂ at C₂), 4.5 (1H, s, NH D₂O exchangeable), 6.2–7.5 (8H, m, ArH), 5.7 (1H, s, NH at 5-position not exchangeable with D₂O due to enaminic NH). Similarly other compounds were prepared (Table 1).

TABLE 1 – PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3*

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅	M.p.**	Yield %
1.	Cl	H	Cl	H	H	245 ^a	54
2.	H	Cl	H	H	H	282 ^b	57
3.	Cl	H	Cl	CH ₃	CH ₃	193 ^c	62
4.	H	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	219 ^b	61
5.	H	CH ₃	H	H	H	120 ^c	70

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

**Solvent for crystallisation: ^aCHCl₃+MeOH (1 : 1), ^bacetonitrile, ^cethanol.